

Exploring Ageing-in-place and Proactive Care Through Vignettes

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ABSTRACT

As the global population ages, the rising demand for social care services has highlighted the unsustainability of current reactive, crisis-driven telecare systems. While proactive care aims to leverage ambient sensing technology for early intervention, its widespread adoption remains elusive due to complex socio-technical challenges. This paper argues that successful proactive care requires alignment across three interacting levels: the Sensing (data) level, the Service (human) level, and the Network (organizational) level. To explore these multi-layered frictions, the study utilises empirically grounded composite vignettes synthesised from a longitudinal observation within a technology manufacturer and focus groups with care providers. Through these narratives, the paper demonstrates the necessity of designing systems that prioritise care capacity and human sensemaking, ultimately aiming to foster proactive care ecosystems that are practically and socially sustainable.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Applied computing** → Health care information systems; • **Social and professional topics** → Seniors; • **Human-centered computing** → Ambient intelligence; Interactive systems and tools.

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KEYWORDS

Ageing-in-place, Proactive Care, Vignettes, Socio-technical systems

1 Introduction

Projections estimate 1.6 billion individuals aged over 65 by 2050, accounting for a rapidly increasing percentage of the population (rising from 10% in 2022 to 16% in 2050) [14]. Technology can provide support and assistance as people age.

Current technology is predominantly reactive; traditional telecare systems intervene after an emergency, such as a fall, takes place. There are around 2 million telecare users in the UK, most commonly using personal alarm pendants or buttons, connected to an Alarm Receiving Centre, that can respond and dispatch support if needed [4]. Consequently, care resources are deployed only after a crisis, and a care provider's understanding of an individual's health is often limited to snapshot visits or post-emergency reports.

A rising demand for social care services accompanies a demographic change towards an ageing population, for example the total expenditure of adult social care in the UK has increased by 8% increase from 2024 to 2025 [3]. Such increases may not be sustainable with current approaches that are labour intensive and reactive. A better approach for health and management of resources would be early intervention, leveraging technology and digitalisation to support independence, shifting from a reactive paradigm to a proactive one, i.e. identifying early signs of decline to prevent emergency situations [1]. However, despite its rising expenditure, and its potential of delivering cost-efficient care

[13], the widespread adoption of proactive care remains elusive.

The transition to proactive care is not merely a technical hurdle requiring better sensors or algorithms; it is a complex socio-technical challenge. Meaningful proactive care requires a cohesive ecosystem: the raw data captured by ambient sensors, the interfaces (dashboards) that facilitate human sensemaking, and the organisational models that intervene and allocate resources. More precisely:

- Sensing level (Data): How we reliably measure behaviour and capture temporal and personalised context without invading privacy.
- Service level (Human): How we draw usefulness from and present complex, ambiguous data so that care providers and families can interpret and trust it.
- Network level (Organisation): How we build business models and resource pathways that support scalable, precursive, and preventative actions over health-related crisis management.

The core contribution of this paper is the empirical demonstration of the socio-technical frictions that hinder the real-world deployment of proactive care. While our ongoing research aims to formalise a comprehensive framework, this workshop paper utilizes a three-level heuristic (Sensing, Service, and Network), derived from systematic qualitative analysis, to structure and expose these multi-layered challenges. By illustrating these frictions, we contribute a set of targeted socio-technical dilemmas designed to drive multidisciplinary discussion within the Interactive Health community on how to align data generation, human sensemaking, and organizational capacity.

2 Constructing the Vignettes

Rooted in qualitative research methodologies, composite vignettes are narrative devices constructed by synthesising empirical data from multiple sources into cohesive, representative stories, while preserving the anonymity of specific individuals and organisations [11]. Rather than acting as purely fictional scenarios, or prescriptive software requirements, composite vignettes are deeply grounded in lived realities, aiming to capture the nuanced emotional, clinical, and organizational complexities of caregiving [6]. In addition, compared to isolated thematic quotes or individual user personas, composite vignettes support the temporal and multi-stakeholder complexity, showcasing the interdependent nature of proactive care ecosystems over extended periods of time.

The composite vignettes presented in this paper are synthesised from a multidisciplinary body of ongoing research [15, 16]. They are empirically grounded from a 30-month longitudinal engaged scholarship observation within an European Assisted Living Technology manufacturer focused on algorithmic development for ambient sensors, combined with insights from focus groups conducted with 23

professional care providers in UK. To construct these narratives, a thematic analysis was first carried out [15]; the data was iteratively coded across the three levels, and the aggregated findings were then structurally synthesized into composite narratives to preserve temporal sequences and participant anonymity.

The vignettes organise complex, multi-stakeholder information to facilitate systematic and collaborative analysis. In the context of this paper, they serve strictly as an analytical tool to explore lived realities, aiming to provoke targeted discussion on how to effectively align raw data, human sensemaking, and organisational capacity in proactive care.

3 Vignettes

3.1 Vignette 1: The Misaligned Care Plan

Context: John, an older adult living alone, receives two daily care visits: a morning visit at 08:00 for breakfast and medication, and an evening visit at 20:00 to assist him into bed. John has difficulty communicating verbally.

The Friction: Care workers report that John is increasingly lethargic, uncooperative during the morning visit, and appears exhausted. Without continuous context, the initial human assumption by the care team is the onset of cognitive decline or a new underlying illness.

The Data Insight (Sensing Level): An ambient sensing algorithm, designed to monitor long-term temporal contexts via Passive Infrared (PIR) sensors, detects a gradual drift in John's routine. Over the past month, his actual bedtime has shifted from 21:00 to 01:00.

The Action (Service Level): The proactive care dashboard translates this raw drift into a contextual insight. The care manager reviewing the dashboard realizes that the 08:00 care visit is forcibly waking John in the middle of his shifted sleep cycle, causing his lethargy and agitation.

The Outcome (Network Level): Supported by this insight, the care organization reassesses John's plan. The morning visit is removed, so visits are aligned with John's circadian rhythm. John is better rested and cooperative, and the care provider successfully optimizes a heavily constrained visiting schedule, freeing up resources.

3.2 Vignette 2: The Hidden Mobility Decline

Context: Margaret lives alone and receives a low acuity care package, consisting of two 30-minute visits a week for help with groceries and cleaning. She is considered highly independent.

The Friction: Over two months, Margaret's walking speed gradually slows down due to the early onset of a urinary tract infection (UTI) and mild osteoarthritis. Because her care worker only sees her briefly twice a week, this slow decline is not detected. The worker assumes Margaret is just having a "slow day." In a traditional reactive system, the first actionable

sign of a problem would likely be Margaret suffering a severe, high-cost fall.

The Data Insight (Sensing Level): Sparse ambient PIR sensors continuously track the time it takes Margaret to move between rooms. Non-parametric statistical testing helps detect a statistically significant reduction in overall gait speed.

The Action (Service Level): The dashboard alerts the central care management team. The dashboard displays the latest downward trend, with a note that lower speeds are associated with fall risks. This visual evidence raises additional care needs and acts as a conversation starter, prompting the care provider to proactively call Margaret.

The Outcome (Network Level): Margaret's family arranges a routine doctor appointment. The early-stage UTI is caught and treated with antibiotics, and the care plan is briefly adjusted to include a daily physical check-in until her mobility recovers. A costly hospital admission is prevented, and Margaret remains safely at home.

4 Discussion

The vignettes organize our multi-stakeholder empirical data to demonstrate that when technology fails to translate from pilot studies to real-world deployment, it is due to friction across distinct socio-technical layers. Using the heuristic of the Sensing, Service, and Network levels, the data illustrates that proactive care cannot scale through technical robustness alone. Consequently, the empirical evidence establishes that active alignment across these boundaries is a structural requirement for practically and socially sustainable care. Complexity across multiple domains, such as the technology, the value proposition, and the wider system, poses a great threat to the scale-up and sustainability of health and care technologies [5]. Furthermore, dissipating forces such as rigid funding timelines and a lack of maintenance infrastructure, often hinder long-term success of care technologies after the initial research funding [8]. From our observations, we highlight two key lessons regarding these barriers:

4.1 Designing for Care Capacity

Despite the cliché that prevention is better than cure, a structural paradox in current care models is that prevention receives little attention as resources are consumed by crisis care. Additionally, social value, such as wellbeing and independence, is difficult to quantify, proactive care services are frequently vulnerable to budget cuts due to unquantified financial worth [2]. There is less capacity for users until they are at a high-level risk, and care providers must prioritise these cases when deploying resources. Therefore, raising alerts for low-risk individuals without providing the time and budget to act on them strains care providers by increasing their burden of responsibility.

Hence, proactive care can become viable in resource-constrained environments if it facilitates resource allocation, rather than simply generating additional work. As

demonstrated in Vignette 1, from the alert raised the care providers successfully identified an opportunity to remove or shift an existing visit rather than add a new one. A metric for organisational return on investment (ROI) is often "Released Capital", to evaluate how the technology can optimise schedules or reduce the need for home support without compromising safety. In Vignette 2, after an initial contact with Margaret, the proactive intervention is appointed to the family, that arranges a routine appointment.

4.2 Designing for Sensemaking

Data density without clear context often increases the cognitive load on already-strained staff, leading to alert fatigue and the eventual abandonment of the platform, due to the invisible work required to sustain it [12].

While algorithms can detect behavioural anomalies, such as the mobility decline in Vignette 2, these alerts cannot be entirely prescriptive.

Instead, proactive alerts trigger a necessary process of sensemaking, as previously reported by Nap et al. [9]. Care providers must evaluate if an anomaly is clinically significant by integrating the digital insight with their existing knowledge of the individual. Therefore, explainability and actionable insights needs to be prioritised [7]. Full automation may not be achievable or desirable; instead, technology should augment human expertise to enable a superior level of personalised service [10]. As demonstrated in the vignettes, the most effective proactive alert functions not as a diagnosis, but as a reliable conversation starter that allows clinicians and care networks to negotiate the appropriate path forward.

4.3 Open Questions for the Workshop

Transitioning to proactive care raises complex ethical and operational dilemmas that require multidisciplinary collaboration. We propose the following open questions to drive discussion within the Interactive Health community:

- How do we balance the end-user's desire for autonomy and privacy (the need to not feel watched or surveilled in their own home) with the family's and care provider's desire for continuous reassurance and objective data?
- How do we effectively evaluate the success of proactive care when the stakeholders involved have competing metrics? (e.g., an older adult's metric of lived independence vs. a family member's peace of mind vs. a care organization's released capital and clinical efficacy).

5 Conclusion

The ambition to move health and social care beyond reaction toward proactive, preventative models is a critical effort for our ageing society. However, placing smart sensors into a home is only a fraction of the solution. This paper highlights

the frictions between the Sensing (data), Service (human), and Network (organizational) dimensions. Using composite vignettes, we show how alignment between the levels can foster timely interventions and resource optimization.

Our future work aims to formalize these qualitative observations into a comprehensive Framework, which will provide structured design principles for aligning these three layers. Additionally, we aim to improve the underlying algorithmic models within the Sensing layer, grounding their technical development directly in the lived requirements and limitations exposed by these socio-technical challenges. By addressing these frictions holistically, we can begin to design proactive care systems that are not only technically robust but practically and socially sustainable.

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